

Three stumbling blocks to the special theory of relativity. About the theory of aberration

A.P. Plyasovskikh

Annotation. Three “stumbling blocks” of the special theory of relativity (SRT) are considered, which are three very simple problems that cannot be solved by SRT methods without changing the conditions and method of solving these problems. Exact sciences require that quantities calculated in different ways under the same conditions have the same meaning. The values of quantities calculated by different methods using SRT at speeds close to the speed of light can differ from each other by unimaginable billions of times. Contradictions that arise when solving problems using SRT require their resolution, since the effects considered by SRT must be taken into account when developing satellite navigation systems. One of the ways to resolve these contradictions is to create alternative theories to SRT (Einstein himself pointed out this possibility). The theory of aberration developed by the author is the first alternative theory to SRT, which has been confirmed experimentally. The theory of aberration allows us to consistently solve the considered and other similar problems.

This work is translated automatically from Russian using Google translator. Original work: Плясовских, А. (2024). Три камня преткновения специальной теории относительности. О теории абберации. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12670038>

Key words: scientific problem, special theory of relativity, SRT, speed of light, relativistic effect, theory of aberration

Table of contents

1. Introduction	2
2. Stumbling block No. 1. Time interval.	3
2.1. Problem 1 about clocks moving towards each other	6
2.2. Controversies that have arisen	10
2.3. On the concept of “relativity of simultaneity”	10
2.4. Controversy in Satellite Navigation Systems	10
2.5. Output 1	11
3. Stumbling block No. 2. Body length.	11
3.1. Introduction	11
3.2. Problem 2 about two rails	12
3.3. Discussion of solutions	15
3.4. Conclusion 2	15
4. Stumbling block No. 3. Reducing spatial distance	16
4.1. Introduction	16
4.2. Problem 3 about reducing space	16

4.3. Controversy	18
4.4. Discussion	18
4.5. Output 3	19
5. Contradictions and ways to resolve them	19
5.1. Ways to resolve contradictions	19
6. Addition. Modification of problem 2 about the length of bodies.	20
7. The theory of aberration is the first alternative theory to SRT, which has been confirmed experimentally. Brief information	24
7.1. Features of the theory of aberration	24
7.2. Law of aberration of physical quantities	26
7.3. Key differences between the theory of aberration and SRT	27
8. Solving problems using the theory of aberration	27
9. Conclusion	28
References	28

1. Introduction

In the exact sciences there is a rule: *different methods of calculating the same quantity should always lead to the same results* (taking into account the permissible error of calculations).

Let us give the following example from Euclidean geometry. Let it be necessary to find the area of a triangle using the formula “The area of a triangle S_1 is equal to half the product of the base a and the height h_a drawn to the base” (Fig. 1, a).

$$S_1 = \frac{1}{2} a \cdot h_a.$$

Fig. 1.

It should be noted that if to calculate the area of a triangle we take its other side b and other height h_b (Fig. 1, b), then we get the same area value

$$S_2 = \frac{1}{2} b \cdot h_b, S_2 = S_1.$$

In air navigation, if we calculate a safe flight altitude in different ways, then no matter how we calculate it, in the end we should get the same value. In aerodynamics, if we calculate the airspeed of an airplane in different ways, then all methods of calculation must lead to the same result.

No matter how we calculate the same value with the same initial data, in all cases we should get the same (identical) value. This is an axiom that is used to confirm the reliability of various formulas and different methods of calculating any quantities in all exact sciences without exception.

If, for example, someone came up with a completely new, previously unknown formula for calculating the area of a triangle, then its accuracy can be easily verified. To confirm the reliability of the new formula, it is enough to calculate the area value in different ways and compare the results. If the results differ from each other, then the proposed formula is erroneous and unreliable.

We also note that without calculating the numerical values of quantities, it is sometimes difficult to verify the reliability or unreliability of any formulas or methods for calculating any quantities.

These are the elementary truths of the exact sciences.

Below we will give three simple examples of calculating three different physical quantities using the methods of the special theory of relativity (SRT), which are so simple that even a smart high school student in general education institutions can understand their essence, not to mention people with higher education, candidates and doctors of science.

We will calculate the time interval, the length of the body and the distance between the bodies in the case of symmetrical movement of two clocks and two bodies relative to each other. The calculations will be done in two different ways.

We will see that in STR different methods of calculating the same (physical) quantity lead to different, contradictory results. This is as if different methods of calculating the area of the same triangle would lead to completely different, completely incompatible results. This is as if different methods for calculating the safe altitude of an aircraft in air navigation would give completely different values, which differ significantly from each other. This is similar to how different ways of calculating the speed of an airplane would lead to values that are completely incompatible with each other. Note here that an incorrect calculation of the safe altitude of the aircraft can lead to a collision of the aircraft with the ground, and an incorrect calculation of the aircraft's speed can lead to the fact that the aircraft reaches supercritical angles of attack and falls into a tailspin.

2. Stumbling block No. 1. Time interval.

Let us present a very simple problem about clocks that move towards each other. The relative speed of movement and the time until the meeting are known based on one clock. You need to find the time before the meeting in the second hour. The solution must be found using the methods of the special theory of relativity (SRT); other methods are prohibited from being used according to the conditions of the problem.

The history of the issue is as follows. In 1905, Albert Einstein's first work on SRT was published, which was called "On the electrodynamics of moving bodies" [1]. In the work, in particular, a revolutionary conclusion for its time was made about the dependence of clock time on the speed of its movement in a stationary reference frame. "Moving clocks go slower than stationary ones," this is the essence of the effect, which is one of the key provisions of this theory. The work [Ibid.], in particular, says:

"If at points A and B of system K there are clocks at rest, synchronously running, observed in the system at rest, and if the clock from point A is moved along the line connecting it with B , towards the latter with speed v , then upon arrival of these clocks in B they are already will no longer be synchronous with the clock in B . A clock that moved from A to B lags behind the clock

that was in B from the very beginning by $(1/2)t(v/c)^2$ a second (accurate to values of the fourth and higher orders), if t is the time during which the clock from A moved to B . It is immediately clear that this result is obtained when the clock moves from A to B along any broken line, and also when points A and B coincide.

If we accept that the result proven for a broken line is also true for a curve continuously changing its direction, then we obtain the following theorem.

If there are two synchronously running clocks at point A and we move one of them along a closed curve at a constant speed until they return to A (which will take, say, t seconds), then this clock, upon arrival at A , will lag behind the clock that remained motionless by $(1/2)t(v/c)^2$. From this we can conclude that a clock with a balancer, located on the earth's equator, should go somewhat slower than exactly the same clock placed at the pole, but otherwise placed in the same conditions."

Let us explain what Einstein means. Let at points A in B on $o c$ and X there are stationary clocks A and B synchronized with each other (Fig. 2). If we take the third clock C , which at the initial moment of time is next to clock A , and is synchronized with them, then when clock C moves to clock B , clock C will lag behind clock B . Simply put, if at the beginning of the journey from point A to point B the moving clock C walked the same way as clocks A and B , then at the end of the journey clock C will lag behind them.

Fig. 2. When clock C moves from clock A to clock B , clock C will lag behind them.

If, in addition, clock C moves along a closed route, then it will lag behind clock A , which was motionless at the starting point (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Having moved along a closed route, clock C will lag behind the stationary clock A .

The provision on slowing down the clock as it moves in [2, p. 156] is formulated as follows: "If you observe a clock from a system in relation to which it moves uniformly at a speed v , then it turns out that it moves $1/\sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}$ several times slower than the same clock stationary in relation to this system."

In a slightly different formulation, this position looks like this: “The clock reading (observed from a system at rest) lags behind by a second per $(1 - \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2})$ second” [1, p. 19].

In work [3, p. 549] the provision on slowing down a moving clock is formulated as follows: “Regarding the system K a clock (a stopwatch whose beats count the seconds - author's note) moves at a speed of v ; when observed from this reference system, not a second passes between the strikes of this clock, but $1/\sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}$ seconds, that is, a slightly longer time. The clock, due to its movement, runs slower than at rest.”

Nobel laureate Richard Feynman expressed this result as follows: “If you watch from the side as an astronaut (of a moving interplanetary spacecraft - author's note) lights a cigarette, it seems to you that he is doing it more slowly than usual, although he himself believes that everything happens at a normal pace. Therefore... instruments for measuring time (“clocks”) must slow down. In other words, when the clock on a spaceship counts down, in the opinion of the astronaut, 1 second, then in the opinion of an outside observer, $1/\sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}$ a second will pass” [4].

In the textbook [5, p. 23-24] the question of slowing down a moving clock is stated as follows: “Let other clocks move rectilinearly and uniformly relative to the inertial frame of reference K . The reference system K' associated with these latter is also inertial. Then the clock in the K' system, from the point of view of an observer in the K system, lags behind in comparison with his clock. And vice versa, from the point of view of the K' system, the clocks in the K system lag. You can verify the absence of any contradiction by paying attention to the following circumstance. In order to establish that the clocks in the K' system lag behind the clocks in the K system, one must proceed as follows. Suppose that at some moment in time the clocks in K' fly past the clocks in K , and at this moment the readings of both clocks coincide. To compare the progress of the clocks in K and K' , it is necessary to again compare the readings of the same moving clocks in K' with the clocks in K . But now we are already comparing these clocks with other clocks in K - with those by which the clock in K' flies at another moment. In this case, it will be found that the clocks in K' will lag behind the clocks in K with which they are compared. We see that to compare the progress of clocks in two reference systems, several clocks are needed in one system and several in the other. Therefore, this process is not symmetrical with respect to both systems. Those clocks that are compared with different clocks in a different reference system will always be lagging.”

How much time, according to STR, will pass according to a moving clock if time passes according to a stationary clock Δt ? In accordance with the situation presented above, in 1 second, according to a stationary clock, $\sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}$ seconds will pass according to a clock moving uniformly and rectilinearly. Accordingly, if seconds pass by a stationary clock Δt , then seconds will pass by a moving clock.

$$\Delta t' = \Delta t \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2} \text{seconds}$$

At a speed of movement v equal to 0.866 the speed of light, this formula takes the form

$$\Delta t' = \Delta t \sqrt{1 - 0,866^2} = 0,5 \cdot \Delta t \text{seconds}$$

If, for example, we observe the astronauts of a spaceship that is moving relative to the Earth at the speed $v = 0,866$ of light c , then in one minute according to our earthly clocks, half as much time will pass on the spaceship, that is, only 30 seconds!

Relevance. Relativistic time dilation, according to SRT, leads to a daily clock error of the GLONASS and GPS satellite navigation systems greater than 7000 ns (nanoseconds, $1 \text{ ns} = 10^{-9} \text{ s}$). The value of the daily lag of the satellite clock compared to the stationary clock on Earth due to relativistic "time dilation" δt in 86400 seconds, that is, per day, is calculated using the formula [1, p.19]

$$\delta t = 86400 \times (1 - \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}) \text{seconds}$$

where v and c are the speed of movement of the navigation satellite and the speed of light, respectively.

GLONASS and GPS satellites move at approximately 3,900 m/s. The speed of light in a vacuum is approximately 300,000 000 m/s.

Moreover, in accordance with existing requirements, the limits of permissible shifts of the national UTC time scale (SU) relative to the UTC coordinated universal time scale are $\pm 3.0 \text{ ns}$ [6]. Thus, the accuracy of the modern state primary standard of units of time, frequency and national time scale is *thousands of times higher than* the value of the calculated daily "relativistic" clock drift of these satellite navigation systems. The contradictions that arise when calculating the relativistic effect of time dilation are an expression of a serious scientific problem, since the magnitude of the error that arises when calculating the deviation of satellite clocks due to this effect is so large that it cannot be neglected under any circumstances.

2.1. Problem 1 about clocks moving towards each other

Let relative to each other with speed v two rows of clocks move (Fig. 4). Each row of watches is rigidly attached to long, solid, for example, metal rods that move parallel to each other in close proximity.

The clocks in each row are synchronized with each other. At the moment of time "00:00:00" (the beginning of the next day), according to the synchronized clocks of one row, the clocks of the other row are also set to "00:00:00" according to the readings of the clocks of the opposite row closest to them. At this point in time, all clocks in both series are synchronized.

Fig. 4. The problem of clocks moving towards each other.

Near clock A , located in the first row, there is observer A . Near clock B , located in the second row, there is observer B . From the point of view of observer A , clock A and all other clocks in the first row are stationary, while clock B and all other clocks in the second row are moving. From the point of view of observer B , clock B and all other clocks in the second row are stationary, while clock A and all other clocks in the first row are moving.

Speed v relative motion of the rows is equal to 0.866 speed of light.

Clock A in the front row and clock B in the second row they are equipped with proximity sensors, for example, hypothetical limit switches that are triggered when these watches approach (pass each other). When the limit switch is triggered, clock A and B are stopped (as a stopwatch is

stopped), after which these watches can be moved so that their readings can be compared by some researcher.

From the point of view of observer A watch B moving towards the stationary clock A with speed v (Fig. 5). In the figure, observer A is indicated by a square.

Fig. 5. Clock movement B relative to the stationary clock A .

Question 1. 1. Calculate what time clock B will show at the moment of stopping when meeting with clock A , if at the meeting clock A will show 100 seconds (“00:01:40,000”)? It is prohibited to introduce additional bodies, clocks or reference systems. The answer to this question must be found using SRT formulas indicating the source (preferably the works of Einstein).

Clue

According to SRT [1, p.19 ; 5, p. 22] the answer can be found using the formula

$$t_B = t_A \times \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2} \text{seconds}$$

where t_A and t_B is the time of clocks A and B , respectively, at the meeting.

At speed $v = 0,866 c$ this formula looks like

$$t_B = 0,5 \times t_A.$$

Solution 1. 1. A simple verbal calculation using the above formula gives the answer: clock B stopped when meeting clock A will show 50 seconds. Let's remember this result: clock reading $A - 100$ seconds, hours $B - 50$ seconds.

Question 1. 2.

Let us now consider this same situation from the other side. From the point of view of observer B , clock A moving towards the stationary clock B at speed v (Fig. 6). In the figure, observer B is indicated by a square.

Fig. 6. Movement of clock A relative to the stationary clock B .

What time will clock B show? at the moment of stopping when meeting with clock A , if at the meeting clock A will show 100 seconds?

Clue

In this case, you need to use a similar formula

$$t_A = t_B \times \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2} = 0,5 \times t_B,$$

where

$$t_B = 2 \times t_A \text{ seconds}$$

Solution 1. 2. An elementary calculation using the above formula gives the answer: clock *B* stopped when it met clock *A* will show 200 seconds. Let us also remember this result: clock reading *A* – 100 seconds, hours *B* – 200 seconds.

Question 1. 3.

After stopping clocks *A* and *B* at the moment of their meeting (Fig. 4), these watches were moved to some researcher to compare their readings.

What readings from this watch will the researcher record?

Solution 1. 3.

Let us recall the results obtained above in answering questions 1 and 2. The reading of clock *A* according to the condition of the problem was equal to 100 seconds.

However, the readings of *the same* clock *B* when calculated in two different ways, they are strikingly different from each other. The first calculation method gave a value of 50 seconds, and the second method - 200 seconds.

This is as if one way of calculating the safe altitude of an airplane gave a value of 200 meters, and the second - 800 meters. But at what flight altitude will the plane not actually collide with the ground?!!

B stopped at the meeting? will they really?

In this example, the readings of clock *B*, calculated in different ways, differ from each other by “only” 4 times. However, if the speed of movement of the clocks towards each other is taken equal to 0.9999 (4 nines after the decimal point) of the speed of light, then the reading of clock *B* when calculated by the first method will be equal to 1.41 seconds, when calculated by the second method - 7,071 seconds. At this speed, the readings *are the same* hours *B*, calculated in two different ways, differ from each other by 5,000 (five thousand) times! At a speed of 0.9999999 (7 decimal points) of the speed of light, the time values of these clocks differ by 5,000,000 (five million) times. At 0.99999999999 (11 decimal places) of the speed of light, clock readings differ by an incredible 50,000,000,000 (fifty billion) times. At a speed of 0.999999999999999 (15 decimal places) of the speed of light - the difference is 500,000,000,000,000 (five hundred trillion) times.

What could be said about the formulas for calculating the area of a triangle if, when calculated in different ways with the same initial data, they led to values that differed from each other by billions or trillions of times?!!

Discussion of solutions

When solving the problem of the readings of the same clock, we have a contradiction. Clock *A*, when meeting according to the conditions of the task at the moment of stopping, will show 100 seconds. However, watch *B* will show, on the one hand, 50 seconds, and on the other hand, 200 seconds. This is impossible. Clock *B* stopped during a meeting cannot show two times at the same time. Stopped clock *B* can show one and only one time value.

It should also be noted that according to the conditions of the problem (Fig. 4), from the point of view of the first and second rows of clocks, there is an absolutely symmetrical picture (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Symmetry of relative motion.

Due to the obvious symmetry of the movement of the two rows of clocks, as well as due to the isotropy of space, clock readings A and B must be the same after they stop, that is, equal to 100 seconds.

When considering the movement of clock B relative to the clocks of the first row (Fig. 5), some of the clocks presented in Fig. 4 are simply excluded from consideration (not shown in Figure 5). Similarly, when considering the movement of clock A relative to the clocks of the second row (Fig. 6), some of the clocks presented in Fig. 4 are also excluded from consideration. However, the exclusion of any watch from consideration does not and cannot have any effect on the operation of the watch in question.

Therefore, the answers to questions 1.1 and 1.2 should be the same. Clock A and B after they stop should show the same time.

However, the answer to the first question already leads to a contradiction. According to the conditions of the problem from the point of view of clock A and B , the motion pattern is absolutely symmetrical. Having answered the first question, we got that after meeting and stopping the clock, clock A will show 100 seconds, and clock B – 50 seconds. Therefore, until the moment of stopping, clock B moved approximately 2 times slower than clock A . But this also means that clock A went 2 times faster than clock B , since they overtook clock B . But what reason led to the acceleration of clock A compared to clock B ? Due to symmetry, clock A and B are equal. They are exactly the same. Clock B moves towards clock A just like watch A moving towards clock B . Between hours A and B there is absolutely no difference. Why watch A walked faster than the clock B ? What physical reason made clock A go faster than clock B ? Scientists - representatives of technical sciences do not have an answer to these questions.

So the contradiction that the answer to the first question leads to is that the symmetrical movement of the clock leads to asymmetrical results.

Clock A and B are exactly the same in design. Why did their testimony at the meeting turn out to be asymmetrical? Due to the symmetry of movement, asymmetry of the clock readings at the moment of their meeting is impossible.

It must be borne in mind that all movement is relative. In relation to the problem considered (Fig. 4), the first row of clocks, on the one hand, is stationary, and the second row is moving. But at the same time, on the other hand, the first row of clocks is moving, and the second row is stationary. Clock B moves relative to clock A , but at the same time (that is, simultaneously) clock A moves relative to clock B . From the point of view of observer A , moving along with clock A , this clock is motionless, and clock B is moving. But from the observer's point of view B , moving together with clock B , this clock is motionless, and clock A is moving.

But can the presence or absence of observers near clocks A or B influence what the readings of these clocks will be at the moment they stop when they meet? Obviously not. The presence or absence of observers near the clock cannot have any effect on its progress. That is why the answers to questions 1 and 2 should be the same. A clock runs *objectively*, whether anyone is watching or not.

Note that one of the methods of “resolving” the contradictions of SRT is changing the conditions or methods of solving the problem. In the exact sciences, checking the correctness of solving a problem is confirmed, in particular, by the fact that different methods of solving it lead to the same results. That is why the contradiction that has arisen needs to be explained without resorting to changing the conditions or methods of solving the problem.

2.2. Contradictions that have arisen

The contradictions that relativistic “time dilation” leads to are that

1. One event occurs simultaneously at two completely different points in time on the same clock;
2. The same clock at the same point in time (the moment the event occurs) shows two completely different times.

In accordance with the law of non-contradiction of formal logic, both the first and the second are impossible. In a more general sense, the contradiction that has arisen is that

3. Calculation of the same physical quantity (the time of occurrence of one event using the same clock) in different ways with the same initial data leads to completely different values that are completely incompatible with each other.
4. Any relative rectilinear and uniform motion of a clock A and B towards each other is absolutely symmetrical. Clock A moves towards Clock B just like watch B moving towards clock A . The contradiction is that SRT leads to asymmetric clock readings A and B when they meet and stop. This simply cannot be. When the watch moves symmetrically, its asymmetrical readings are impossible.

2.3. On the concept of “relativity of simultaneity”

The question arises: can the concept of “relativity of simultaneity” help explain the contradiction that has arisen? According to the principle of “relativity of simultaneity”, if two events separated in space are observed simultaneously in a “moving” with speed $v > 0$ reference system, then they will be observed non-simultaneous relative to the “stationary” system.

However, in SRT this concept is applicable only if there are two events separated in space. In our case, there is only one event: two clocks A and B meet nearby when moving relative to each other, and at the moment of approaching they stop. The clock stops only once. Therefore, the same stopped clock cannot have two readings at the same time.

That is why the relativity of simultaneity in this case does not help explain the contradiction that has arisen.

2.4. Controversy in satellite navigation systems

In relation to satellite navigation systems GPS, GLONASS and others, the following contradiction occurs.

On the one hand, satellites move in orbits relative to the earth's surface. Therefore, according to SRT, there should be a slowdown in the clocks of navigation satellites and, accordingly, their lag behind the clocks on Earth.

the GPS or GLONASS satellite clock compared to the stationary clock on Earth must be at least 7000 ns.

But, on the other hand, from the point of view of observers on satellites, the satellites are motionless, and the clocks on the earth's surface move relative to them. Therefore, from the point of view of the clocks on the satellites, the opposite effect should occur, that is, the clocks on Earth should run slower than the clocks on the satellites. In other words, the clocks on satellites per day should move ahead compared to earthly clocks by at least 7000 ns.

The contradiction is that satellite clocks, on the one hand, must lag behind earthly clocks. On the other hand, satellite clocks must run faster than earth clocks. But how do satellite clocks actually tick without taking into account "gravitational time dilation" (the actual difference in elapsed time between two events, measured by observers at different distances from the gravitating mass)?

On the third hand, the clocks of navigation satellites located in one orbit move relative to the clocks of navigation satellites located in another orbit. Therefore, some clocks in satellite navigation systems must lag behind other clocks. Which clocks of satellite navigation systems will lag behind others if all orbits have the same parameters (the same altitude and, accordingly, the same speed)?

If we assume that one row of synchronized clocks is located at the equator of some planet rotating at high speed, which has no atmosphere, and the other row of synchronized clocks moves in a circular orbit at a very low altitude (in this case, gravitational time dilation, due to its smallness, can be neglected), then which clock will run slower: a stationary clock on the surface of a rotating planet, or a moving clock in orbit? From the point of view of an observer moving in orbit along with the clock, the clock in orbit is stationary, and the clock on the surface of the planet, on the contrary, is moving.

2.5. Conclusion 1

So, stumbling block No. 1 of SRT is that when solving the simplest problem of the readings of a clock that has stopped during a meeting, different methods of calculating the readings of the same clock lead to completely different results that are incompatible with each other. At a speed close to the speed of light, the calculated values of clock readings can differ from each other by unimaginable billions and trillions of times! This is as if the flight altitudes of the same aircraft, calculated in different ways, differed from each other by billions of times!

3. Stumbling block No. 2. Body length.

3.1. Introduction

The history of the issue is as follows. In the work "On the electrodynamics of moving bodies" [1], it was concluded that moving bodies are reduced in size. The contraction occurs along the velocity vector.

If, for example, a car is racing along the road at high speed, then its length measured on the road will decrease, but the width and height of the car will remain the same. The reduction in

length occurs in the proportion $1:\sqrt{1-(v/c)^2}$, where v and c are, respectively, the speed of movement of the body (in our case, a car) and the speed of light.

If we, being in a spaceship, observe through the window a solid meter ruler moving past us in the direction of its length, then we record that its length is equal to $\sqrt{1-(v/c)^2}$, that is, it has become shorter.

If the speed of the ruler is equal to 0,866 the speed of light, its length will be only 50 cm (half a meter). At this speed, all moving bodies are reduced by approximately half.

The effect of shortening the length of moving bodies is called *Lorentz contraction*.

The length of a moving body, measured in a fixed coordinate system, is determined by the formula [5, p. 27]:

$$l = l_0\sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}, \quad (1)$$

where l_0 is the body's own length (body length at rest).

How to measure the length of a moving body

Consider the question of how to measure the length of a long car moving along the road at high speed. The vehicle's speed is unknown.

Fig. 8. Measuring the length of a car moving at high-speed using synchronized shots.

For this purpose, you can use the “method of synchronized shots”. To implement this method, you will need two synchronized clocks installed at the beginning and end of the car, as well as two small-caliber rifles that fire down simultaneously according to the signals from the synchronized clocks. Rifles should be located near the clock at the beginning and end of the vehicle. It's simple. At some predetermined (planned) point in time, according to clock signals that are synchronized with each other, the rifles must fire synchronized downward shots. After the shots, the bullets will make marks on the road, measuring the distance between which you can measure the length of a car moving at high speed (Fig. 8).

3.2. Problem 2 about two rails

Let's consider two rails, the length of each of which at rest is 4 m (Fig. 9 a). On the surface of each rail there is a length scale with divisions of 1 mm (as on a regular measuring tape).

Let two synchronized clocks with lasers be attached to the first rail, which, based on the clock signals, simultaneously send two pulsed laser beams towards the second rail. The distance

between lasers on the first body is 1 meter. The rails are located parallel to each other in close proximity. Lasers leave marks on the surface of the second rail.

Let these rails move relative to each other at a speed of 0.866 times the speed of light. From the point of view of observers located on the first rail, this rail is at rest, and the second rail is moving (Fig. 9, b).

Fig. 9 a. Two four-meter rails in a stationary state. The distance between lasers on the first rail is 1 meter.

Fig. 9 b. The second rail moves relative to the first at a speed of $v = 0,866 c$. The length of the second rail was halved. The length scale on the second rail was also doubled. What distance between the laser marks on the second rail will be recorded by the compressed length scale on the surface of the second rail?

Fig. 9 c. The first rail moves relative to the second at a speed of $v = 0,866 c$. The length of the first rail was halved. The length scale and distance between lasers on the first rail have also been halved. What distance between the laser marks will be recorded on the surface of the second rail?

According to SRT, due to Lorentzian contraction, the length of the second rail, measured on the scale of the first rail (in the reference system associated with the first rail), will decrease and become equal to

$$l = l_0 \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2} = 4 \sqrt{1 - 0,866^2} \approx 2 \text{ meters,}$$

where l_0 is the own length of the second rail, equal to 4 m.

From the point of view of observers located on the first rail, the second rail will become shorter, it will compress in the longitudinal direction by exactly 2 times. Together with the second rail, the length scale printed on the surface of the second rail will also shrink. It looks as if a regular length scale was drawn on a rubber band stretched 2 times, like on a construction tape, and then the rubber band was returned to its original state. In this case, the scale on the rubber band will shrink by 2 times.

At that moment, when the second rail flew past the first, two synchronous pulses of laser beams were sent, which left two marks on the second rail, which had shortened in length.

After this, the second rail was stopped and sent to some researcher.

Question 2.1: What distance between the laser marks on the scale on the second rail will this researcher record?

Solution 2.1.

In this case, you need to use the formula

$$l_2 = \frac{l_1}{\sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}},$$

where l_1 is the distance between the lasers on the moving first rail (Fig. 9 b);

l_2 – unknown distance between the laser marks on the second rail.

Calculation using this formula gives

$$l_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - 0,866^2}} = 2 \text{ m.}$$

We found that the distance between the laser marks on the scale on the second rail, calculated by the first method, is 2 meters. Let's remember this result.

Note that all movement is relative. The second rail moves relative to the first rail. But at the same time, at the same time, the first rail moves relative to the second rail. From the point of view of observers located on the second rail, the second is motionless, and the first rail is moving (Fig. 9 c). Therefore, from the point of view of observers located on the second rail, the first rail will become exactly 2 times shorter than the second. In this case, along with the first rail, the length scale printed on the surface of the first rail will also shrink. In addition, the distance between the lasers located on the compressed first rail will also shrink by 2 times. On the scale of the second rail, this distance will become equal to 0.5 meters.

At that moment, when the first compressed rail flew past the second, two synchronized pulses of laser beams were sent, which left two marks on the second rail.

After this, the second rail was sent to some researcher.

Question 2.2 : What distance between the laser marks on the scale on the second rail will this researcher record?

Solution 2.2.

The calculation leads to the result

$$l_2 = l_1 \times \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2} = 1 \times \sqrt{1 - 0,866^2} = 0,5\text{m.}$$

Thus, the distance between the laser marks on the scale on the second rail, calculated by the second method, is 0.5 meters. Let's remember this too.

We have looked at the same relative motion of two rails from two points of view. In this case, two lasers sent synchronous beams towards the second rail only once. The laser marks in the first case (question 2.1) and the laser marks in the second case (question 2.2) are the same. They are examined from different angles. After two lasers made two marks on the second rail, the second rail was sent to some researcher.

Question 2.3. What distance between these laser marks on the scale on the second rail will the researcher record?

Solution 2.3. In the first case, we found that the distance between the marks on the second rail turned out to be equal to 2 m. However, the second method of calculation gave an answer four times smaller: 0.5 m. Different methods of calculating the same value led to completely different, completely incompatible results. with different meanings.

At a speed of 0.9999999999 (11 decimal places) of the speed of light, these values differ from each other by 50,000,000,000 (fifty billion) times.

3.3. Discussion of solutions

Obviously, if two lasers stationary on one rail simultaneously make only two marks on the other rail, then no matter from which side we view these rails, there will be only two of these marks. There can be only one distance between these marks on the scale of the second rail, on either side. SRT shows that when calculating this distance in two different ways, we get different values, which is completely impossible.

If we consider the fast movement of a car along the road (Fig. 8), we get a similar contradiction. If we consider a moving car relative to a stationary road, then by measuring its length using the method of synchronized shots, we can obtain that the length of the car has decreased compared to its length when stationary. However, if we consider movement from the other side, then from the point of view of the driver of the car, the car is motionless, but the road and everything that is on it are moving. From this point of view, all longitudinal distances on the road should be reduced. If a length scale is applied to the surface of the road, it will shrink in the same way as a pre-stretched rubber band, on which a length scale is applied when stretched, compresses. Therefore, from the point of view of the driver and passengers of the car, measuring its length using the method of synchronized shots should show that the car, on the contrary, has become longer than when stationary.

Let us hypothetically measure the length of a 10 - meter car that is moving at a speed of 0.866 *s*. Calculations using the first method (the road is stationary, the car is moving) lead to the conclusion that the distance between the bullet marks on the road will be equal to 5 m. Calculations using the second method (the car is stationary, the road is moving) lead to the fact that the distance between the marks of the same bullets on the road will be equals 20 m.

3.4. Conclusion 2

So, stumbling block No. 2 of SRT is that in calculations related to the length of a moving body, different calculation methods lead to completely different results that are incompatible with each other. When the speed of movement is close to the speed of light, the calculated values of the

length of the body or the distance between points on the body can differ from each other by billions of times! This is as if the flight altitudes of the same aircraft, calculated in different ways, differed from each other by billions of times!

4. Stumbling block No. 3. Reducing spatial distance

4.1. Introduction

One of the interesting consequences of Lorentz contraction is the reduction in spatial distance (space compression), which supposedly takes place when astronauts move on a fast-flying interstellar spacecraft.

If the ship flies at a speed of 0.866 times the speed of light, then the distance to the stars ahead along the direction of the ship's movement will be reduced (as in the case of measuring the length of bodies) by exactly half. If the ship rushes at a speed of 0.9999999999 (11 decimal places) the speed of light, then the distance to the stars ahead along the ship's flight path will be reduced by approximately 220,000 (two hundred twenty thousand) times.

The distance ahead of the spacecraft is determined by the formula

$$s = s_0 \times \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}, \quad (2)$$

where s_0 is the distance at rest.

SRT theoretically opened up to humanity the possibility of intergalactic travel.

However, let's do some calculations.

4.2. Problem 3 about reducing space

Let in the first frame of reference K at the origin of coordinates O there is a stationary observer A . A long absolutely solid wire is stretched along the X -axis of the K system, on which a length scale is applied (such as on a regular measuring tape). At a distance of 0.5 au (astronomical units¹) from the origin at point B of the X axis there is a (stationary) laser attached to the wire B . The same laser A is located at the origin near observer A . In the figure, lasers are indicated by arrows.

The second reference frame moves relative to frame K K' , the X' axis of which is parallel to the X axis and is in close proximity to it. The X and X' axes are directed towards each other. An absolutely solid wire with a length scale is similarly stretched along the X' axis of the second system K' . The origin of the coordinate system K' moves towards the origin of the coordinate system K , with speed v . At the origin of coordinates of the second system K' there is an observer C stationary in this system.

At the origin of coordinates of the system K' , next to the observer C , a mirror C is fixed, indicated in the figure by a small rectangle. Same mirror D fixed on a wire at point D of the X' axis.

Let at some point in time, based on a signal from a synchronously running clock located next to lasers A and B , the lasers send pulsed beams towards the X' axis. At this moment in time, mirror C was opposite laser B , and mirror D was opposite laser A .

Laser beams are reflected from the mirrors (the reflected beams are indicated by dotted arrows), after which they leave marks on the wire X of the first system K .

We need to answer two questions:

1. At what distance from the observer C (the origin of coordinates of the system K') is the mirror D located?

¹1 astronomical unit (AU) is the average distance from the Earth to the Sun. 1 au = 149,600,000 km.

2. At what distance from each other will the reflected laser beams leave marks on the X axis wire, stationary in the first reference system K ?

Fig. 10 a.

Fig. 10 b.

Fig. 10 c.

From the point of view of observer A , the first system K is stationary, and the system K' is moving. In accordance with this, all solid scales, that is, rulers fixed in the first system K will not change in length, and rulers located along the X' axis of the second K' are compressed (reduced) in length in proportion to the coefficient $k = \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}$. At equal $\sqrt{0,75} \approx 0,866$ speed, v the

proportionality coefficient k is 0.5. In other words, at this speed, from the point of view of observer A , the length scale on the wire of the X' axis of the moving system K' will be compressed exactly twice (Fig. 10 b). Therefore, according to the scale compressed by half on the moving wire X' , the distance between the mirrors C and D will be equal $|CD| = 2|AB| = 2 \times 0,5 = 1$ to au

So, laser beams will be reflected from mirrors C and D , located in the system K' at a distance 1au from each other.

Let's consider the relative motion of observers with lasers and mirrors from the other side. From the point of view of observer C , mirrors C and D are stationary in the frame K' ; and lasers A and B are moving at speed v . In addition, from the point of view of observer C , a wire X with a system length scale K is also moving. Consequently, this wire with the scale will compress in accordance with the Lorentz contraction by exactly 2 times (Fig. 10 c). Therefore, on the compressed wire, the reflected laser beams will leave marks, the distance between which will be 2 au, that is, twice as much as the distance between the mirrors, equal to 1 au.

Let's note the following. A pulsed beam emitted by a laser at point A (Fig. 10 a), reflected from mirror D almost an instant later (the distance between the wires is almost zero according to the condition) ended up at point E (Fig. 10c). The distance $|AE|$ is 1.5 au. It turns out that the laser beam A traveled a distance of 1.5 a in an instant. that is, but this cannot be.

4.3. Contradiction

Having made the assumption that when moving, the space in the moving reference frame is reduced, we came to a contradiction, according to which a laser beam emitted at point A of the system K , reflected from the mirror D in the immediate vicinity, almost an instant later made a mark at point E on a wire of the K system, covering a distance of 1.5 a in an instant. e. (Fig. 10 c). This cannot be because the distance is 1.5 au light travels in approximately 750 seconds. In an instant, light cannot travel a distance of 750 light seconds.

4.4. Discussion

The problem considered so far has only theoretical rather than practical significance in space flights. For example, GLONASS satellites revolve around the Earth in circular orbits, the altitude of which is 19,100 km. The radius of the Earth is approximately 6300 km. Therefore, the diameter of the satellites' orbits is 50,800 km. The speed of the satellites is approximately 3,900 m/s, the speed of light is 300,000,000 m/s. Using formula (2), it can be calculated that due to the Lorentz contraction, the orbits of the satellites are compressed by approximately only 0.00429 m or 4.29 mm.

The Voyager 1 spacecraft is currently located 24,410,849,000 km from Earth, moving away from it at a speed of about 17,000 m/s. The Lorentz shortening of this distance is 39,190 m.

These Lorentz reduction values are quite small and can be ignored when solving practical problems of satellite navigation and spacecraft navigation.

But let's imagine that in some future humanity decided to send an intergalactic expedition to explore the Universe.

Having calculated that the flight will hypothetically take place at a speed of 0.9999999999999999 (13 decimal points) of the speed of light, the astronauts will be confident that, thanks to the Lorentzian contraction, the space in front of the spacecraft will shrink approximately 2,200,000 times, due to which the speed of their movement will seem to increase by the same amount. In a year of flight, according to the astronauts' watches, they will be able to fly a distance of 2,200,000 light years. The distance from Earth to the Andromeda Galaxy is approximately 2,500,000 light years. Therefore, apart from the time required to accelerate the spacecraft, astronauts will believe that they will reach this galaxy in just over a year.

However, solutions to problems 1-3 showed that the astronauts' calculations may be erroneous. The distance that astronauts need to fly to Andromeda, on the one hand, is approximately 2,500,000 sv. years. But, on the other hand, this same distance is approximately 1.1 sv. years.

But what if it turns out that in a real space flight the space in front of the spacecraft does not shrink? This question is forced to be raised by the contradictory results of calculations made when solving problems 1-3.

4.5. Conclusion 3

Stumbling block No. 3 of SRT is that in calculations related to distances between bodies, different calculation methods lead to completely different results that are incompatible with each other.

5. Contradictions and ways to resolve them

The contradictions obtained when solving problems 1-3 using STR methods can be formulated as follows: different methods of calculating the same quantity under the same conditions lead to different results that are absolutely incompatible with each other. At speeds close to the speed of light, the values of the same quantity, calculated by different methods, can differ from each other by billions (!) of times.

This is unacceptable in the exact sciences. The same quantity at the same time under the same conditions cannot simultaneously take on two different values that are completely incompatible with each other. The same clock, when stopped (see solution to problem 1), cannot show two different times at the same time. The same body cannot simultaneously have two completely different lengths, measured on the same scale (see problem 2). A distance measured in different ways cannot have two different, incompatible values on the same scale at the same time (see problem 3).

These contradictions require their resolution, and these requirements put forward practical problems of satellite navigation that need to be solved. As has been shown, the daily relativistic drift of satellite clocks is, according to SRT calculations, 7000 ns, which is thousands of times higher than the requirements for the accuracy of the primary time standards. Therefore, relativistic effects cannot be ignored in modern satellite navigation systems.

However, among scientists in the technical sciences there is no understanding of how to use SRT methods to solve problems similar to problems 1-3, and how to resolve contradictions that arise when solving these problems [7-12].

5.1. Ways to resolve contradictions

One of the ways to resolve contradictions that arise when solving problems related to relativistic effects (including in satellite navigation systems) is to search for the causes of contradictions and resolve them without going beyond the scope of SRT. It should be noted that the “relativity of simultaneity” has not been shown to help resolve these contradictions, so an alternative solution should be sought.

Einstein himself indicated another way to resolve contradictions. He believed that “for the same set of experimental facts, there may be several theories that differ significantly from each other” [3, p. 593]. That is why, according to the founder of STR, alternative theories that differ significantly from the theory of relativity not only can, but should exist. The history of science confirms the truth of this statement by Einstein. Alternative theories are: the geocentric system of

the world of Ptolemy and the heliocentric system of the world of Copernicus; Euclidean geometry, as well as the geometry of Riemann and Lobachevsky; Darwin's theory (natural selection) and the theory of creationism (creation of the world). Currently, there are dozens of theories of gravity that are alternative to the general theory of relativity (GTR) (the author of one of them is MSU professor A.A. Logunov). This list of alternative theories in science goes on.

That is why you should pay attention to the way of resolving contradictions, which the founder of SRT himself points to: the alternative theory of aberration to SRT, developed by the author of this article. This theory will be discussed below.

6. Addition. Modification of problem 2 about the length of bodies.

Let's consider problem 2 in the following modification.

Let exactly the same rails as in the second problem move past each other. On the first rail, lasers are also installed at a distance of 1 m from each other, which, based on signals from synchronized clocks, simultaneously emit pulses of laser beams (Fig. 9 a).

The difference is that the surface of the second laser is a translucent mirror, with a length scale applied to its surface. The laser beams first leave two marks on the scale of the second rail, then, partially reflected from the mirror surface, return to the first rail and leave two marks on the scale of the first rail.

The task is to use different methods, alternately assuming that first the first rail is stationary and the second is moving, then that the first rail is moving and the second is stationary, at a relative speed of movement of 0.866 times the speed of light (according to the SRT, at such a speed moving bodies contract exactly in twice), calculate the following values:

- 1) The distance between the marks of two lasers on the scale of the second rail;
- 2) The distance between the marks of reflected laser beams on the scale of the first rail;
- 3) Find the coordinates of all laser marks on the scales for the cases presented in Fig. 11 and 12.

The problem is solved in two steps.

First step : find the distance between the laser marks on the second rail:

Case 1: the first rail is stationary, the second is moving (Fig. 11, a);

Case 2: the first rail is moving, the second is stationary (Fig. 11, b).

The reflected pulses of laser beams are located at a distance from each other equal to the distance between the laser marks on the second rail.

It can therefore be considered that, regardless of the first step, two pulsed laser beams were emitted from the second rail towards the first, and the distance between the laser beams was equal to the distance between the marks on the second rail.

Second step : find the distance between the laser marks on the first rail, provided that the distance between the beams on the scale of the second rail is known (calculated in the first step).

Case 1: the first rail is stationary, the second is moving;

Case 2: the first rail is moving, the second is stationary.

Fig. 11. Step 1 of solving the problem: a) – the second rail moves relative to the stationary first rail; b) – the first rail moves relative to the stationary second rail.

Fig. 12. Step 2 of solving the problem:

a) – Case 1 of step 1, the second rail moves relative to the stationary first rail; b) – Case 1 of step 1, the first rail moves relative to the stationary second rail; c) – Case 2 of step 1, the second rail moves relative to the stationary first rail; d) – Case 2 of step 1, the first rail moves relative to the stationary second rail.

Commentary on the solution to the problem.

Step 1 of solving the problem gives two different values of the distance between the laser marks on the scale of the second rail, namely 2 m and 0.5 m (Fig. 11). Contradiction 1: according to the conditions of the problem, each of the lasers emitted one pulse of laser light, which left only two marks on the second rail. The distance between two marks on the scale of the second rail is the same, and this distance cannot take two different values. In the same way, the same person at the same time cannot be both 150 cm and 190 cm tall.

Step 2 of solving the problem gives 4 different values of the distance between the marks of the reflected laser beams on the scale of the first rail, namely 0.5 m, 1 m, 2 m and 4 m (Fig. 12). Contradiction 2 is the same: two laser beams can leave only two marks on the scale of the first rail, the distance between which can have one and only one value.

As noted in the introduction, different methods of calculating the same quantity should always lead to the same results.

Let's find the distance between the marks on the first rail left by laser beams reflected from the second rail in one more way.

For laser beams located on the first rail, the surface of the second rail is a conventional mirror moving in close proximity to the rail. Since the distance between direct laser beams towards the mirror is 1 m, the distance between the laser beams reflected in the opposite direction from the mirror is also 1 m (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13. Reflection of laser beams from a moving mirror.

It would seem that the only correct solution has been found, but this is not so. If you compare Figures 12, a and 12, d, you can see that in this case there is ambiguity in the distance between the marks on the second rail.

What to do with the distance values between the marks on the first rail of 0.5 m, 2 m and 4 m? In the exact sciences, different methods of calculating the same quantity should *always* lead to the same results.

So, we have clearly shown that different methods of calculating the same quantity using SRT lead to different results that are completely incompatible with each other. This represents a stumbling block for the STO.

7. The theory of aberration is the first alternative theory to SRT that has been confirmed experimentally. Brief information

According to Einstein's insightful statement, a complex of physical phenomena and experimental data can be described by many completely different theories ².

Alternative theories not only can exist, but also inevitably must appear in order to improve a coherent and consistent scientific picture of the world (the building of science). However, the modern building of science cannot yet be called perfect, as evidenced, for example, by the mysteries of "dark energy" and "dark matter", which have not yet been solved. According to observational data from the Planck space observatory published in March 2013, the total mass-energy of the observable Universe consists of 95.1% dark energy and dark matter ³, but no one knows what it is. And perhaps one of the alternative theories to SRT will help solve the greatest mysteries of modern science, which include the mysterious dark energy and dark matter.

The aberration theory is the first alternative theory to STR, which is confirmed by two experiments [13-20]. One of these experiments was carried out by a team of 100 scientists and engineers in St. Petersburg in 2022 [21, 22]. The scientific publication about this experiment, according to the "international register of achievements and records," received the title "Property of the Nation" [23-25]. In addition, the reliability of the Aberration Theory is confirmed by the results of another experiment conducted by scientists from the National Institute of Standards and Technology NIST in Boulder (USA), who observed the most accurate clocks on our planet for 14 years [26, 27].

The theory of aberration is most fully presented in monographs [13, 14].

A shortened presentation of the theory of aberration is presented in [17].

In addition, popular scientific versions of the theory of aberration have been published [15, 16].

Works devoted to the theory of aberration can be purchased at litres ⁴, or found in Internet search engines using the keywords "Plyasovskikh, theory of aberration, alternative to SRT."

The list of scientific works in the Russian-speaking space can be found on the website <https://elibrary.ru> by typing in the search bar the name of the author "Plyasovskikh A P" and the keywords "theory of aberration", "alternative to SRT", "aberration".

7.1. Features of the theory of aberration

The theory of aberration, like STR, is based on two well-known postulates (principles) of the constancy of the speed of light and relativity. In addition, the theory of aberration adds an additional *principle of aberration* (deviations, changes) *of the location of* a body moving relative to the observer, from which, in turn, follows *the principle of aberration of the physical quantities* of this body (distance to the body, size of the body, speed of the clock located on the body, speed of movement of the body, and so on).

²Einstein A. On the special and general theory of relativity (public presentation) Collection. scientific tr. Volume 1 (M.: Nauka, 1965) p. 530

³Wikipedia. Dark energy.

⁴Books by Plyasovsky A.P. on the theory of aberration on liters: <https://www.litres.ru/author/ap-plyasovskih>

Fig. 14. Aberration (deviation) of the location of a body moving relative to the observer.
Aberration of the distance to a moving body.

The essence of these principles is very simple. According to the principle of *aberration location* of the body, the observer sees (observes, records) a body moving relative to him not in the place where it actually is (not in its *true location*), but in another, *observed location* (Fig. 14). The reason for this effect is the movement of the body and the delay in the receipt of information to the observer about the location of the body due to the finite speed of electromagnetic waves (light), using which the observer receives information.

The physical meaning of the principle of body location aberration can be explained by the following example. Let's imagine that at Sheremetyevo Airport (Moscow), an aircraft has taken off and is heading to St. Petersburg. Let the crew continuously report on the location of the aircraft and these reports are received by the Pulkovo dispatcher, but information about the location does not travel at the speed of light (as is the case with radio communications) but much slower, at the speed of sound equal to approximately 330 m/s. The distance from Moscow to St. Petersburg is approximately 650 km. Sound will travel this distance in approximately 33 minutes. Let's imagine that information about the location of this aircraft is displayed automatically against the background of the map on the controller's monitor. But at the moment when the controller sees on the monitor that the plane is taking off at Sheremetyevo, in fact it will already be approximately halfway between Moscow and St. Petersburg. The true position of the aircraft and its observed position will differ from each other due to the delay of information about the position of the aircraft, which is moving towards the controller at the speed of sound (in our example).

The same picture will occur when monitoring an aircraft using radar, or using hypothetical binoculars, with which you can see the aircraft at any distance, even in Sheremetyevo. Only when using electromagnetic waves for observation, the deviation of the observed location from the true location of the aircraft will of course be less.

The speed of Halley's comet when flying past the Earth is approximately 70 km/s, the minimum distance from the Earth to the comet is 0.15 AU. e. At this distance and at this speed, the

deviation of the observed position of the comet from its true location is approximately 5200 km (for comparison: the radius of the Earth is 6300 km).

The principle of aberration of physical quantities is that when measuring the speed of movement of a body, the distance to a moving body, the course of a clock located on the body and many other quantities, due to the same effect, there is a deviation (aberration) of the measured (observed) values of these measured quantities from their true values. A special case of the principle of aberration of physical quantities of a moving body is the Doppler effect, according to which the frequency of electromagnetic oscillations measured by the receiver when the transmitter moves relative to the receiver deviates from the true (natural) frequency of the transmitter. It should be noted that the principle of aberration of physical quantities of a moving body does not follow from the Doppler effect and is not a consequence of the Doppler effect.

7.2. Law of aberration of physical quantities

In the theory of aberration, a new, previously unknown *law of aberration of physical quantities of a body moving relative to the observer was discovered* [13, 14, 20].

This law is formulated as follows:

The observed quantities of a body moving along the line connecting it and the observer are directly proportional to the same true quantities.

A complete list of body quantities that obey this law: the distance from the observer to the body; the path traveled by the body; body length; speed of body movement; the pace of time passing on the clock located on the body; time interval measured by a clock located on the body; frequency of the radiation source located on the body; angular velocity, circular (angular) frequency and frequency of rotation of a material point around a circle; angular velocity, circular (angular) frequency and frequency of rotation of a body around an axis; circular frequency and frequency of oscillations of rectilinear harmonic oscillations of a material point, as well as the frequency of a periodic process occurring on the body. The law of aberration is subject to 16 quantities (perhaps there will be more in the future).

In mathematical form, the law of aberration has the form:

when the body approaches the observer

$$Q_{obs} = \frac{Q_{tr}}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}},$$

when the body moves away from the observer

$$Q_{obs} = \frac{Q_{tr}}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}},$$

in general

$$Q_{obs} = \frac{Q_{tr}}{1 \pm \frac{v_{tr}}{c}},$$

where Q_{obs} and Q_{tr} are the observed and true values of the body, respectively;

v_{tr} and c are the true speed of the body and the speed of light, respectively;

plus sign - when the body moves away from the observer, minus - when the body approaches him.

The generalized law of aberration of physical quantities of a moving body is formulated as follows: the observed physical quantities of a body moving uniformly and rectilinearly relative to the observer are directly proportional to these same true quantities.

Generalized in mathematical form the law of aberration has the form:

$$Q_{obs} = \mu \times Q_{tr},$$

where the proportionality coefficient μ is determined by the formula

$$\mu = \frac{1}{\cos \sigma + \frac{v_{tr}}{c} \cos \alpha},$$

α is the angle between the direction to the true location of the material body and the velocity vector;

σ is the aberration displacement (the angle between the direction to the true and the direction to the observed location of the body).

The coefficient μ can be written in the form

$$\mu = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v_{tr}}{c}\right)^2 \sin^2 \alpha + \frac{v_{tr}}{c} \cos \alpha}}.$$

(In this expression, under the square root sign, the denominator contains only the first two terms.)

For small v_{tr} (and, accordingly, small (v_{tr}/c)) expressions for μ take on the simple form

$$\mu = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c} \cos \alpha}.$$

7.3. Key differences between the theory of aberration and SRT

The most significant differences between the theory of aberration and SRT are as follows.

1. The true dimensions of moving bodies remain unchanged. In SRT, a moving body contracts in size along the line of motion.
2. The observed dimensions of moving bodies vary depending on speed, and on the relative location of the observer and the moving body. In SRT there are no concepts of the true and observed size of bodies; in SRT these are one and the same thing (which is why some paradoxes of SRT arise).
3. The true course of a moving clock remains unchanged. In SRT, moving clocks go slower than stationary clocks.
4. The observed progress of a moving clock varies depending on the speed of movement and the relative location of the observer and the moving clock. As the clock approaches the observer, its observed rate accelerates, and as the clock moves away from the observer, its observed rate slows down. In SRT there are no concepts of true and observed clock movement. In SRT these are one and the same thing, which is the reason for some paradoxes.
5. There are no paradoxes in the theory of aberration, such as the twin paradox, the “pole and barn” paradox, and so on. SRT is replete with paradoxes.
6. The theory of aberration does not exclude the relative motion of bodies at superluminal speeds. In the SRT there cannot be superluminal motion of bodies. (In space, however, there are objects moving at superluminal speeds [19].)
7. The theory of aberration is amazingly beautiful. The beauty of physical and mathematical theory is expressed by symmetry, proportionality of parts, their similarity and harmony. The formulas for transformations of true and observed physical quantities of a moving body in the theory of aberration have multifaceted symmetry, they are surprisingly harmonious. Due to the fact that few people understand SRT, it is quite difficult to judge the beauty of this theory.

8. Solving problems using the theory of aberration

Solving the clock problem. In the theory of aberration, a distinction is made between the true course of a clock, which can be observed by an observer located next to the clock, and the observed course of a clock distant from the observer. The true progress of a clock does not depend

on the speed of its movement. A moving clock moves (meaning its true progress) in exactly the same way as a stationary clock. That is why, if watch *A*, *stopped during a meeting*, shows 100 seconds, then watch *B* at the moment of stopping, they will show exactly the same time, that is, 100 seconds.

Solving problems about the length of bodies. In the theory of aberration, a distinction is made between the true sizes of bodies and their observed sizes. The true dimensions of bodies do not change when they move. Therefore, in problem 2, if the true distance between the lasers on the first body was equal to 1 m, then the distance between the laser marks on the second body was also exactly 1 m.

Likewise, the true length of a car as it moves along the road remains the same.

Solving problems about the distance between bodies moving in space. In the theory of aberration, space does not compress when bodies move. The true distances between moving bodies change in accordance with Newtonian mechanics.

9. Conclusion

The article presents three “stumbling blocks” of SRT - three problems, the solution of which in different ways using SRT leads to different values that are absolutely incompatible with each other. At a speed of movement close to the speed of light, the values of the same quantity calculated by different methods under the same conditions can differ from each other by billions (!) of times. This is as if the area of the same triangle, calculated in different ways, differed from each other by billions of times. This is as if the values of the safe altitude of an airplane, calculated in different ways, also differed from each other by billions of times.

A consistent solution to the three problems presented within the framework of SRT is apparently impossible. (Provided that the conditions of the problems and methods for solving them do not change.)

However, the practical needs of solving problems arising in the development of satellite navigation systems require consistent consideration of the SRT effects under consideration.

Resolving contradictions that arise when solving problems using SRT methods is possible in two main ways. One of the ways is to search for the causes of contradictions and resolve them without going beyond the scope of SRT.

Another way to resolve contradictions was indicated by Einstein, who believed that “for the same set of experimental facts, there may be several theories that differ significantly from each other.” In accordance with this, there may be alternative SRT theories that will consistently and non-paradoxically describe the phenomena of the reality around us.

The theory of aberration developed by the author of this article is the first alternative theory to SRT that has been confirmed experimentally. With the help of the theory of aberration, the considered problems are solved in a consistent and non-paradoxical way.

Bibliography

1. Einstein A. On the electrodynamics of moving bodies // Collection. scientific tr. – T. 1. – M.: Nauka, 1965. – P. 7-35.
2. Einstein A. The principle of relativity and its consequences in modern physics // Collection. scientific tr. – T. 1. – M.: Science. – 1965. – P. 138-164.
3. Einstein A. On the special and general theory of relativity // Collection. scientific tr. – T. 1. – M., Science. – 1965. – P. 530-600.

4. Feynman lectures on physics. T. I (1–2) / Richard Feynman, Robert Leighton, Matthew Sands; [transl. from English O. A. Khrustaleva, G. I. Kopylova, A. V. Efremova]. – M.: AST Publishing House, 2019. – 448 p.
5. Landau L. D., Lifshits E. M. Theoretical physics: Textbook. manual : For universities. In 10 volumes. T. 2. Field theory. – 7th ed. rev. - M.: Nauka, 1988. 512 p.
6. State verification scheme for time and frequency measuring instruments. (approved by Order of Rosstandart dated September 26, 2022 N 2360).
7. Plyasovskikh AP Eshmuradov DE Which formula of special theory of relativity is true? // International Scientific Journal "Science and Innovation". Series A. Volume 2 Issue 3. 03/30/2023. - R. 302-312. URL: <http://scientists.uz/view.php?id=4185> ; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7786468>
8. Plyasovskikh, A. P. On the issue of using formulas of the special theory of relativity in satellite navigation / A. P. Plyasovskikh // Scientific Bulletin of the State Research Institute of Civil Aviation. – 2023. – No. 43. – P. 136-144. – EDN WKLWNY. URL: <https://gosniiga.ru/upload/docs/vestnik/%D0%92%D1%8B%D0%BF%D1%83%D1%81%D0%BA%20%E2%84%9644,%202023%20%D0%B3.pdf>
9. Plyasovskikh, A. P. The special theory of relativity gives errors of 100 times or more / A. P. Plyasovskikh // Radio navigation and time: proceedings of the North-West Radio Center of the Almaz-Antey East Kazakhstan Concern. – 2023. – No. 11(19). – pp. 134-147. – EDN PINVMQ. <https://noc.goz.ru/local/templates/nots/docs/riv11.pdf>
10. Plyasovskikh, A.P. Dialogue between a relativist and a realist about the relativistic effect of “time dilation” // Modern scientific research and innovation. 2024. No. 2 [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://web.snauka.ru/issues/2024/02/101490> (date of access: 02/10/2024).
11. Plyasovskikh, A. (2024). Dialogue between a relativist and a realist about the relativistic effect of “time dilation.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10613574>
12. Plyasovskikh, A. (2024). Dialogue of a relativist with a realist about the relativistic effect of "time delay". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10613662>
13. Plyasovskikh A.P. Theory of aberration. The first theory alternative to the special theory of relativity [Electronic resource]. – M.: Znanie-M, 2023. – 503 p. – [ISBN 978-5-00187-483-6](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10613662)
14. Plyasovskikh AP Eshmuradov DE Theory of aberration – an alternative to the special theory of relativity. – T.: “Fan va texnologiyalar mashriyot-matbaa uyi » 2024.432 p. – ISBN: 978-9910-748-53-0
15. Plyasovskikh A. P. The theory of aberration - the first theory alternative to the special theory of relativity: popular presentation: [Electronic resource] / A. P. Plyasovskikh. – Moscow: Knowledge-M, 2023. – 55 p. – [ISBN 978-5-00187-493-5](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10613662)
16. Plyasovskikh Alexander Petrovich. (2023). The theory of aberration is the first theory alternative to the special theory of relativity. Popular summary. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8150872>
17. Plyasovskikh Alexander Petrovich. (2023). The theory of aberration is the first theory alternative to the special theory of relativity. Brief summary. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8151586>
18. Plyasovskikh Alexander Petrovich. (2023). Theory of aberration. Popular science presentation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8250637>

19. Plyasovskikh A.P. On the possibility of moving bodies at superluminal speed. — LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing, 2021. – 152 pp. – [ISBN 978-620-4-71514-8](#)
20. Plyasovskikh A.P. The law of aberration and its applications in navigation and air traffic control. - M.: Znanie-M, 2022. - 70 p. — [ISBN 978-5-00187-223-8](#)
21. Abdulmanov T.M. and others. Experiment to measure the observed rate of movement of a moving clock // Automation and Software Engineering. 2022, No. 4(42) URL: <http://www.jurnal.nips.ru/sites/default/files/AaSI-4-2022-4.pdf>
22. Plyasovskikh AP Eshmuradov DE Experiment on measuring the observed rate of a moving clock // International Scientific Journal "Science and Innovation". Series A. Volume 2 Issue 3. 03/24/2023. - R. 169-188. URL: <http://scientists.uz/view.php?id=4089>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.776773>
23. Russian scientists have refuted Einstein's special theory of relativity <https://bloknot.ru/nauka/rossijskie-ucheny-e-oprovergli-spetsial-nuyu-teoriyu-otnositelnosti-e-jnshtejna-1061085.html>
24. Russian scientists have refuted Einstein's special theory of relativity <https://www.ecopravda.ru/nauka/rossijskie-ucheny-e-oprovergli-spetsialnuyu-teoriyu-otnositelnosti-ejnshtejna/>
25. Scientists from Russia have refuted Einstein's special theory of relativity <https://actualnews.org/exclusive/458600-ucheny-iz-rossii-oprovergli-specialnuju-teoriju-otnositelnosti-jejnshtejna.html>
26. Plyasovskikh, A.P. The most accurate experiment refuting the special theory of relativity // Modern scientific research and innovation. 2023. No. 9 [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://web.snauka.ru/issues/2023/09/100840> (date of access: 09/30/2023).
27. Plyasovskikh, A. P. An experiment refuting the special theory of relativity / A. P. Plyasovskikh // Science and innovation - modern concepts: a collection of scientific articles based on the results of the International Scientific Forum, Moscow, October 05, 2023. – Moscow: Infiniti, 2023. – P. 107-111. – EDN MRBQSQ. https://elibrary.ru/download/elibrary_54673816_25635964.pdf

A.P. Plyasovskikh

St. Petersburg State University of Civil Aviation named after Air Chief Marshal A. A. Novikov
st. Pilotov 38, 196210 St. Petersburg, Russian Federation

Email: al.plyasovskih@yandex.ru